

digital humanities climate coalition

Digital Humanities Climate Coalition Project Self-Assessment Tool v1.0

DHCC Project Self-Assessment Tool (v1.0)

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This self-assessment tool is intended to support Digital Humanities practitioners, researchers, technicians, curators, software engineers, and related professionals seeking to embed environmental sustainability into their project design, delivery, and reporting.

The tool is divided into 8 areas:

1. Project Design
2. Equipment Procurement & Reuse
3. Data Management
4. Web Design
5. AI and Computational Work
6. Travel and Collaboration
7. Catering
8. Project Legacy

In line with the [EPSRC AREA framework for responsible research and innovation](#), we recommend using the prompts below to reflect on how your project design, delivery, and reporting might *Anticipate*, *Reflect on*, *Engage with*, and *Act to mitigate* the environmental impacts of your work.

Researchers who have used this checklist in their project design, and who are satisfied that they plan to act appropriately, may include the following wording in their funding application:

“This project aligns with the Digital Humanities Climate Coalition’s 2026 recommendations on embedding environmental sustainability and climate justice into project design.”

Optionally, during project design, the DHCC recommends giving your project a score for each area based on your planned actions and writing a short narrative to justify that score. At a suitable mid-point in your project, return to the score and justification and update as appropriate. Then, at the end of the project, the tool and your responses to it can be used to review progress made, adaptations that took place, successes, failures, and any gaps between anticipated action and reality. This exercise is not intended to create feelings of blame or individual responsibility. Rather, it is hoped that Digital Humanities practitioners will use the tool to ensure they act with [integrity and accountability](#) – in the context of what is possible – to realise their ambitions for environmental justice.

1. Project Design

Responsible innovation should be considered as an integral part of the research design and project lifecycle, with environmental and ethical commitments revisited iteratively as the project develops, rather than treated as a one-off consideration. Reflection and reflexivity should be formalised within the project's governance structures, with clear processes for review and accountability, ensuring that responsible innovation actively shapes decision-making across research design, implementation, and dissemination.

How do I design for the future?

	✓
Have you embedded environmental sustainability considerations into the research questions, methodologies, and/or project processes ?	
Have you established milestones within the project lifecycle to review and revise environmental commitments and assumptions as the research evolves?	
Have resources been allocated to measure, monitor, and report the environmental impact during the project?	
Have you identified who is responsible for overseeing environmental considerations within the project governance structure?	
Have you considered how stakeholder perspectives (e.g. affected communities, practitioners, or interdisciplinary partners) inform environmentally responsible design choices?	
Have you considered which design choices may inhibit attempts to identify, measure, and monitor the environmental impact of your work?	

2. Equipment Procurement & Reuse

The manufacturing processes of research equipment are carbon and resource intensive ([De Paepe, et al. 2024](#)). Researchers should therefore reuse and recycle resources, equipment, materials and consumables where possible. When planning purchases, researchers should seek advice from technical experts, such as technicians. The below practices apply most clearly to laboratory research but are transferrable to all research settings.

How can I reduce unnecessary purchases whilst keeping my research feasible?

	✓
Have you checked whether your institution has an existing policy and process for reusing existing equipment ?	
Have you checked internal inventory and asset registries for existing equipment and consumables, and limited/reduced new purchase requests accordingly?	
Can you use second-hand or reconditioned equipment, and commit to doing so wherever feasible?	
Can you share equipment with other researchers/organisations?	
Will you consider passing on usable items when no longer needed through initiatives like the UniGreenScheme ?	
Have you budgeted reusable alternatives to single-use plastics, or to minimise plastic consumables?	

3. Data Management

Sustainable Data Management Plans (DMPs) ensure that data generated during research projects are managed, stored, shared, and preserved responsibly and efficiently, with long-term accessibility and minimal environmental impact in mind.

How do I manage research data sustainably and efficiently?

	✓
Will you collect data using standard, non-proprietary file formats for long-term accessibility?	
Will you use green data centres and cloud services with low-carbon impact to store data? If corporate policies make this unfeasible, will you lobby for change?	
Will you choose a data sharing repository with a sustainable business model compliant with FAIR principles ? Have you considered the CARE principles as an alternative?	
Have you considered data retention timeframes (often 5–10 years post-project) using a repository with robust preservation policies?	
Have you considered the energy consumption of your chosen data storage option ?	
Will you use data compression techniques and delete unnecessary data ?	

4. Web Design

Designing a project-specific webpage can be a valuable method of disseminating results, sharing knowledge, and widening the impact of outcomes. The [W3C Web Sustainability Guidelines \(WSG\)](#) provide a set of principles and success criteria for creating digital products and services that reduce environmental impact and improve user experience. These guidelines, similar to those from [Minimal Computing](#) and broader sustainability and accessibility frameworks, help teams make responsible design decisions that align with environmental justice and inclusive access.

How can my web presence reflect my commitments to environmental justice?

	✓
Will you align design and development decisions with the W3C Web Sustainability Guidelines (WSG) and revisit them as they are updated?	
Will you evaluate and measure your website's environmental impact (e.g. using tools such as Website Carbon , Cardamon , or Ecograder), and consider setting a page weight budget to monitor and reduce energy use?	
Will you evaluate green web hosting options, for example by using the Green Web Check , to prioritise renewable energy and responsible providers?	
Will you reduce digital dependencies (software stacks) and consider whether static websites and minimalist content management systems are appropriate?	
Will you review third-party services using Are My Third Parties Green? to check and report their impact?	
Will you seek to design accessibly and inclusively , using progressive enhancement to support older browsers and devices?	

5. AI and Computational Work

Computationally intensive research practices such as AI, blockchains, and large-scale data processing, are often referred to as Maximal Computing. As these approaches become increasingly embedded within research methods and digital infrastructures, they carry significant environmental costs, particularly in terms of energy use, carbon emissions, and resource consumption. A critical assessment is needed to establish whether such techniques are necessary, proportionate, and responsibly deployed.

How do I adopt environmentally responsible approaches to large scale digital and computational work?

	✓
If you are planning on using AI , have you considered alternative approaches that are less computationally intensive?	
Can you use less-intensive compute processes ? (e.g. smaller models, and improved utilisation of existing institutional infrastructure)	
If you are planning machine learning tasks, will you evaluate performance relative to compute cost , rather than optimising accuracy alone?	
Will you complete an Algorithmic Impact Assessment (e.g. https://canada-ca.github.io/aia-eia-js/) before using an AI tool?	
Will you incorporate a grid aware computing approach ?	
Will you engage critically with Big Tech? Will you examine the sustainability implications of mainstreaming deep learning AI?	

6. Travel and Collaboration

All projects – not only those led by Digital Humanities practitioners – should take into account the environmental impact of travel. This is because all travel incurs a carbon cost, with flying contributing the largest share of emissions by individual researchers ([Flying Less in Academia 2023](#)). However, travel is an essential component of research, for fieldwork, archival visits, networking, dissemination, public engagement, etc. These activities are particularly important for the development of early career colleagues. Considering the ‘value of emissions’ will help you balance concerns about climate justice with concerns about researcher efficacy and fairness.¹

How do I minimise my environmental impact whilst also optimising the value attached to travel?

	✓
Will you consider the purpose of your travel, and establish whether the value gained justifies the travel?	
Will you consider who to involve in travel and how many people need to travel? <i>Consider equality/career development opportunities (e.g. for early career colleagues) and if working with partners in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMIC), consider the importance of democratisation of research processes and co-production principles.</i>	
Will you explore lower-carbon travel options , taking into account relative cost/time implications? <i>For example, could you travel by train? Could you opt for a direct flight?</i>	
Will you consider the length of your stays? Can you get more value if you stayed longer, or maybe avoid a subsequent journey?	
Can you use virtual meeting spaces as an alternative or supplement to flying? <i>Consider budgeting for an online facilitator. You may need to consider investing in infrastructure especially in LMICs to support this.</i>	
Have you checked whether there is an institutional travel policy to enforce travel decisions? If not, will you consider developing a green travel policy?	

¹ Our thanks to Louise Ackers and Laurence Kenney for sharing their concept of ‘Value for Carbon’ (personal communication, December 9, 2024).

7. Catering

Hosting events is an important aspect of research. Academic conferences and networking or public engagement events require catering budgets, sometimes for large numbers of attendees. However, our choices of food and drink impact our environmental impact. They also provide an opportunity to involve wider communities in the choices that support reducing the environmental impact of a Digital Humanities project.

How do I use food as a tool for change?

	✓
Have you checked whether your institution has a sustainable catering policy ?	
Can you consider only providing catering for major public-facing events ?	
Have you budgeted primarily for plant-based food , with meat available only as an opt-in option?	
Have you prioritised locally sourced and seasonal foods to reduce transport and emissions ?	
Have you considered the environmental impact of drinks , including minimising single-use plastic bottles and providing water stations or reusable cups?	
Are you able to choose suppliers or caterers that actively track and report the carbon impact of their offerings?	

8. Project Legacy

Be explicit about the environmental impact beyond project completion. Consider how lessons learned will be documented and shared to support accountability, inform wider sector guidance, and contribute to collective improvement. Pay particular attention to identifying, de-aggregating, and reporting supply chain ([Scope 3](#)) emissions, so that longer-term and indirect impacts are made visible and can inform future decision-making.

	✓
Have you reviewed data archiving and long-term maintenance of digital outputs?	
Have you considered how project outputs (e.g. data, tools, methods, publications) can be reused or adapted to reduce duplication and environmental impact in future research?	
Have you assessed how hardware purchased for the project will be maintained or reused in future work?	
Will you plan for the responsible decommissioning or disposal of project materials and infrastructure at project completion?	
Do you have a plan for reporting on the project's environmental impact and sharing knowledge with colleagues and the wider community?	

What legacy do I want to leave?

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